

EXPLORING THE PHONETIC VARIATION OF ENGLISH LOANWORDS IN THE PASHTO LANGUAGE: A PRAAT-BASED ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of the Pashto language on English loanwords, with particular focus on lexical borrowing and the adaptation of modern concepts and technological terms. With around 50 million native speakers, Pashto has evolved significantly in response to globalisation, migration, and the emergence of social media. This research focuses on the incorporation of English words into Pashto, paying specific attention to variations in vowel sounds. Using PRAAT software for phonetic analysis, the study reveals notable differences in the pitch and intensity of borrowed English words, exemplified by the word "copy," which shows a decrease in pitch and an increase in intensity when pronounced in Pashto. By systematically examining these phonetic variations, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of the dynamic nature of language adaptation and the ongoing interaction between English and Pashto, suggesting avenues for further research in linguistic evolution.

Introduction

Pashto, also known as Pakhto or Pukhto, is an Eastern Iranian language primarily spoken by the Pashtun ethnic group in Afghanistan and Pakistan. It has nearly 50 million native speakers and was declared Afghanistan's national language in 1936 (Hallberg, 1992). Pashto is one of Afghanistan's two official languages. It is also a significant regional language in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan and in some areas of Balochistan. The Pashto language boasts a rich oral literary tradition dating back a thousand years, long before its earliest known written records, which appeared in the 16th century and were standardised by Bayazid Ansari. Notable literary figures, such as Pir Roshan (Bayazid Ansari), often regarded as the father of Pashto literature, and Khushal Khan Khattak, significantly shaped classical Pashto literature (Raverty, 1860). Modern Pashto consists of two primary dialects: a soft dialect (southern), spoken in Kandahar, Quetta, and the southern regions of Afghanistan and Pakistan, and a hard dialect (northern), spoken in Peshawar, Swat, and the northern regions of Afghanistan and Pakistan (Ahmed, 1976). The syntax of the Pashto language follows a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) structure.

The English language is a West Germanic language that primarily originated in early Medieval England. It is a blend of various linguistic influences, with approximately 60% of its vocabulary derived from French, around 20% from Latin, and another 20% from Old English (Finkenstaedt & Wolff, 1973). Today, it is one of the most widely spoken and studied languages in the world. English has its foundational vocabulary and grammar rooted in the language of Germanic tribes, namely the Angles, Saxons, and Jutes, who are now associated with present-day Germany and Denmark (Crystal, 2003). The language spoken by these tribes is known as Old English. Norse significantly influenced this version of the language through the Viking invasions between the 8th and 11th centuries and through Latin during the process of Christianization. In 1066, the Norman invasion introduced a host of French words, giving rise to what we call Middle English (Barber et al., 2009). This period marked a significant evolution in the language, which became more standardised through the works of authors like Geoffrey Chaucer, and its use in schools and courts. By the 15th century, a major vowel shift occurred, and the invention of the printing press helped standardise spelling and grammar, leading to the emergence of Modern English, as exemplified by Shakespeare's works (Baugh & Cable, 2013). Over time, English spread across the globe through British colonialism and is

now widely regarded as the world's lingua franca—a common language for international communication and business (McIntyre, 2020). Today, English is one of the official languages in numerous countries and is spoken by billions of people as either a first or second language. Additionally, English follows a Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) word order. Currently, English has almost 1.5 billion speakers worldwide.

The influence of English on Pashto began in the late 20th century due to several factors, including migration, globalisation, media and technology, the education systems in Pakistan and Afghanistan, and social media. One of the most visible effects of English on Pashto is lexical borrowing, the incorporation of loanwords into the language. Common English loanwords in Pashto include "mobile," "computer," "file," "school," "office," and "doctor," among others. This linguistic change emerged as Pashto speakers interacted with new inventions and concepts, often using English terms, especially in educated settings and urban areas. The adoption of these words has enriched Pashto vocabulary but has also sparked discussions among linguists regarding the preservation of the language's purity (Hassan, 2025; Hassan et al., 2025).

Similarly, this study aims to explore the influence of English on Pashto, particularly the words it has adopted. The researchers in the current study have examined variations during the adaptation process. This investigation has been conducted systematically and scientifically using PRAAT software, focusing on variations in the pitch and intensity of English adopted words and sounds in Pashto language.

Research Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods research design integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches. The qualitative component involved interpreting observations and conducting interviews with students from various districts, including *Malakand*, *Shangla*, *Swat*, *Buner*, *Lower Dir*, and *Upper Dir*, at Riphah International University. The researchers conducted 50-minute interviews with 30 students, and the recordings were securely stored. In the quantitative aspect of the study, the researchers employed PRAAT software to analyse the pitch and intensity of the recorded sounds, focusing on phonetic variations. Fifteen words were selected for scrutiny using PRAAT, examining both the original English pronunciations (extracted from online sources) and their Pashto adaptations (recorded by the researchers, all native Pashtuns). The pitch and intensity features were checked and validated using PRAAT's spectrogram. Notable

variations were observed in vowel sounds, including the conversion of long to short vowels and vice versa. Similar alterations were found with consonants, exemplified by the transformation of the 'f' sound into a 'p' sound and many more.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of English Adopted Words in Pashto with Variations in Vowel Sounds

This study presents an in-depth analysis of the phonetic variations observed in English loanwords integrated into Pashto, shedding light on the complex processes of adaptation these terms undergo. Using PRAAT (Boersma, 2001), the research quantitatively examined various sound characteristics, including pitch, intensity, and duration, for a selection of English words borrowed into Pashto. The findings reveal not only phonetic exchange but also the cultural and contextual factors shaping the transformation of these loanwords.

Conversion of sound "o" to "a:"

Case Study of the Word "Copy". The term "copy" in English commonly refers to the act of creating something that resembles or is identical to the original in shape or content, particularly in academic and artistic contexts. This word has been borrowed in Pashto with a slight variation. For instance, in English, the "o" in "copy" is pronounced with a short "ɒ" sound, which transitions into a longer "a:" sound in Pashto, while the final "y" shifts from a short "i" sound to a prolonged "i:" sound. These changes are not just phonetic; they also involve noticeable variations in pitch and intensity when spoken. To illustrate, the English word "copy" resonates at 1833 Hz, a noticeably higher pitch than its Pashto counterpart, "kapee," which registers at 1491 Hz. Furthermore, while "copy" has a frequency of 2938 Hz, the Pashto "kapee" has a higher frequency of 3096 Hz.

Figure 1: Spectrogram of the word copy

The same applies to the variation in word order and the hotspot described in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Pitch and Intensity of English words adopted in Pashto, showing variation of the vowel “o.”

SN	English word	Pitch/Intensity	Phonemic Transcription	Adopted in Pashto	Pitch/Intensity	Phonemic Transcription
1.	Copy	1833/2938Hz	/kɒp.i/	kapee	1491/3096Hz	/ka:pi:/
2.	Order	3417/3590Hz	/ɔ:də/	Aader	3008/3783Hz	/a:dəɾ/
3.	Hotspot	2807/4043Hz	/hɒt.spɒt/	Haas paat	3149/3622Hz	/ha:s'pa:t/

Conversion of the long “u:” to short “u”:

Analysis of the word “Cooler.” The term "cooler" in English refers to a device designed to maintain cool air or cold water and to store beverages or preserve food. This word shows a slight pronunciation variation when borrowed in Pashto. In English, the term is pronounced "cooler," with a long "u:" sound. However, when adopted into Pashto, it is pronounced “coler,” with a shorter “u” sound. Further analysis also reveals that the pitch of the English word "cooler" is approximately 3301 Hz. In contrast, the Pashto "coler" is pronounced at a lower pitch of 2701 Hz. Additionally, the intensity of the original term "cooler" is 3333 Hz, while the Pashto equivalent "coler" is 3254 Hz.

Figure 2: Spectrogram of the word “cooler” and “coler.”

A similar variation can be seen in other words, where the long vowel sound /u :/ is replaced by the short /u/ as shown in the table 2 below:

Table 2: *Pitch and Intensity of English words adopted in Pashto*

SN	English words	Phonemic Transcription	Pitch/Intensity	Adopted in Pashto	Pitch/Intensity	Phonemic Transcription
1	Cooler	/ku:lə/	3301/3333Hz	Culer	2701/3254Hz	/kulər/
2	Boot	/bu:t/	3149/3991Hz	But	2991/3964Hz	/but/
3	Suit	/su:t/	3374/3331Hz	Sut	3546/3051Hz	/sut/
4	Loot	/lu:t/	3310/3116Hz	Lut	2987/2771Hz	/lut/

Analysis of the Word “Light”

Conversion of diphthong “ai” to short “e”. The term “light” in English refers to the fundamental natural phenomenon that stimulates our vision and enables us to perceive objects. This word has seamlessly entered the Pashto language, albeit with a subtle pronunciation variation. For instance, the phonetic structure of the original word “light” contrasts with its Pashto counterpart, which is pronounced “let.” Notably, there is a distinct change in the vowel sounds: the English diphthong “ai,” heard in “light,” transforms into the more open “e” sound in the word “let.” Furthermore, an interesting aspect lies in the sounds' intensity: the original English “light” resonates at 3030 Hz, conveying a brighter, sharper tone, while the adapted Pashto “let” has a softer quality at 2793 Hz.

Figure 3: Spectrogram of the word light:

Analysis of the Word “Waistcoat”

Conversion of diphthong “ei” to the long “a:” sound. The term "waistcoat" refers to a stylish garment that covers the upper body, leaving the arms uncovered. Characteristically, it features a row of buttons running down the front and is typically worn over a dress shirt, serving both form and function in formal and semi-formal attire. This word has entered the Pashto language, albeit with a slight pronunciation variation that reflects the language's phonetics. For instance, the original English pronunciation of "waistcoat" (/weɪskəʊt/) features a distinctive diphthong, which is altered in its Pashto equivalent, "waskat" (/wɑːskʌt/). Notably, the English diphthong "eɪ" transitions to the "ɑː" sound in Pashto, illustrating the word's adaptation to local phonology. Similarly, the English diphthong "əʊ" becomes the simpler "aː" sound in Pashto, highlighting the nuances of language contact. In terms of auditory properties, the pitch of "waistcoat" is notably higher at 3396 Hz compared with "waskat" at 2664 Hz, reflecting differences in regional speech patterns. Furthermore, the original sound "waistcoat" has a frequency of 3288 Hz, exhibiting stronger resonance than "waskat," which has a frequency of 2577 Hz in Pashto.

Figure 4: Spectrogram of the word waistcoat

Phonetic Analysis of English loanwords in Pashto: Consonant Sound Variations

Conversion of “f” to “p” in “fridge.”

The term “Fridge” is a common shorthand for “refrigerator.” Interestingly, this word has been incorporated into Pashto with a slight phonetic variation. To illustrate this, consider the sound patterns of both words: the first pattern reflects the English pronunciation of “Fridge,” while the second shows how it is articulated in Pashto as “Pridge.” A notable transformation occurs in consonant sounds: in English, the initial “f” becomes “p” in Pashto, resulting in the pronunciation “Pridge.” There is a difference in the pitch of the original English word “Fridge”, which is measured at 3280 Hz, distinctly higher than its Pashto borrowed form, “Pridge,” which is at 2991 Hz. Additionally, there is a contrast in intensity: the original word “Fridge” has an intensity of 3701 Hz, while the borrowed Pashto version “Pridge” reaches a higher intensity of 3964 Hz.

Figure 5 : Spectrogram of the word “Fridge” and “Pridge.”

Conversion of “f” to “p” and short “i” to “e” in the word “tiffin.”

The term "tiffin" originates from South Asian English and refers to a specific type of utensil used to carry food. For instance, the English word "tiffin" is borrowed in Pashto as "tepun," where the consonant sound of "f" is replaced with the "p" sound, while the short "i" vowel in "tiffin" extends into a longer "e" sound in "tepun." Moreover, an interesting acoustic comparison reveals that the English word "tiffin" has a higher pitch, at 3385 Hz, compared to the borrowed Pashto version "tepun," which resonates at 2964 Hz. Additionally, the intensity levels further illustrate this distinction: "tiffin" has a higher intensity of 3859 Hz, while "tepun" slightly trails at 3807 Hz.

Conversion of “f” to “p” in the word “fashion.”

The term "fashion" refers to a widely embraced contemporary style that encompasses clothing, hairstyles, decor, and even social behaviours. This concept has been incorporated into the Pashto language, though its pronunciation has undergone a subtle change. In Pashto, the original word "fashion" is nuanced by a change in the initial consonant: the "f" sound is replaced with a "p" sound, yielding the locally pronounced "pashion." A notable distinction can be observed in the acoustic qualities of these two words. The pitch of the English term "fashion" is approximately 3611 Hz, which contributes to its articulate, sharp sound. In comparison, the Pashto variant "pashion" has a slightly lower pitch of 3245 Hz, giving it a mellower timbre. Furthermore, the intensity of "fashion" is 3740 Hz, which is distinctly higher than that of "pashion" (3654 Hz).

Table 2: *Pitch and Intensity of English words adopted in Pashto with conversion of “f” sound into “p”.*

SN	English words	Pitch/Intensity	Phonemic Transcription	Adopted in Pashto	Pitch/Intensity	Phonemic Transcription
1.	Fridge	3280/3701Hz	/frɪdʒ/	Pridge	2991/3964Hz	/prɪdʒ/
2.	Tiffin	3385/3859Hz	/tɪfɪn/	Tepun	2964/3807Hz	/tepun/
3.	Fashion	3611/3740Hz	/fæʃən/	Pashion	3245/3654Hz	/pæʃən/
4.	Frying Pan	3008/3310Hz	/fraɪɪŋ ,pæn/	Prepan	2857/2857Hz	/pre:pɑ:n/

Analysis of the Word “Dustbin”

Conversion of “s” to “z”. The term “dustbin” refers to a container specifically designed for the disposal of household waste, typically placed outdoors for convenience in refuse collection. This word has seamlessly integrated into Pashto, undergoing a slight yet noticeable change in pronunciation. To illustrate, the original English word “dustbin” features a distinct sound pattern, while its Pashto counterpart, “duzbin,” incorporates a subtle variation in the consonant sounds. In this adaptation, the sharp “s” sound in the English version is replaced by a softer “z” in the Pashto version, reflecting the language’s phonetic nuances. Furthermore, an analysis of the pitch reveals intriguing differences between the two versions. The English word “dustbin” resonates with a pitch of approximately 3439 Hz, which is notably higher than that of the Pashto word “duzbin,” measured at around 2599 Hz. Despite this variance in pitch, it is interesting to note that the intensity of sound remains consistent for both words, with “dustbin” in English recorded at 2987 Hz, while “duzbin” in Pashto also registers at the same intensity level of 2987 Hz. This illustrates not only linguistic adaptations but also the fascinating interplay between phonetics and cultural exchange.

Figure 6: Spectrogram of word *dustbin*

Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate the phonetic variations observed when English words are assimilated into Pashto. To explore this linguistic shift, the researchers compiled a list of English words that have entered the Pashto language. Employing advanced spectrographic analysis with PRAAT software, they sought to illuminate the subtle yet significant shifts in pronunciation that these borrowed words undergo. The findings revealed a unique transformation: as English words transition into Pashto, they do not merely retain their original forms; rather, they undergo a range of phonetic alterations. Through a comprehensive examination of both the borrowed terms and their English counterparts, the researchers uncovered a distinct pattern: the pitch and intensity of the original English words consistently exceeded those of their Pashto adaptations. For instance, the English word *cooler* elegantly morphs into *culer*, while *copy* becomes *kapee*. Even more examples showcase this phonetic variation: *hotspot* reconfigures as *haaspaat*, *dustbin* shifts to *duxbin*, and *fridge* takes on the adapted form *pridge*. This research primarily contributes to our understanding of the adoption process in Pashto, a language that embraces borrowed words while imposing its own conditions (Hassan, 2025). As highlighted in the analysis section, English words have been incorporated into Pashto but are adapted to fit the language's specific requirements and local context. This study also recommends that future researchers explore more local Pashto dialects, as English loanwords may be pronounced differently across these variations.

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